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Does the Right to Services help to establish Good Governance? An analysis of Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act 2010

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Abstract

This paper examines the effectiveness of the Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA), 2010 in establishing good governance. The paper uses Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) for evaluating the MPPSGA, 2010. The WGI framework comprises six broad governance dimensions: voice and accountability, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, control of corruption, and political stability and absence of violence/terrorism. The paper uses a mixed research methodology including an ex-post facto approach, analytical approach, quantitative research, and qualitative research to examine the MPPSGA, 2010. The study's findings indicate that the following Act does not fulfil all the requirements for good governance defined by the WGI. The paper also provides recommendations for improving the MPPSGA, 2010 to achieve good governance.

Keywords: *Right to Service, Public Service Guarantee Act, Good Governance Indicator, voice and accountability, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, control of corruption.*

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Introduction:

In recent years, many countries have focused on improving their traditional governance systems to good governance. Scholars have different definitions of good governance, and there is no consensus between them. Different organizations and scholars have formulated different interpretations of it. Daniel Kaufmann and Aart Kraay developed the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) in 1996, under the auspices of the World Bank, to help measure good governance. This study focuses on analysing the Right to Service (RTS)/Public Service Guarantee Act (PSGA) about the WGI to determine whether it helps establish good governance. RTS/PSGA is a legislative Act that requires service providers to deliver a service within a specified time and holds them accountable if they fail to do so. Based on RTS, the Madhya Pradesh (India) State Legislative Assembly passed a bill to this effect.

Good Governance and Worldwide Governance Indicators:

Worldwide governance indicators have been used to examine the role played by the above Act in establishing good governance. Therefore, it becomes necessary to discuss governance, good governance, and worldwide governance indicators to develop an understanding of them.

Governance: The customs and institutions that a nation uses to exert its authority make up its governance. This includes the method by which governments are chosen, scrutinized, and replaced; the capability of the government to develop and implement sound policies successfully; and the respect of citizens and the state for the institutions that regulate their interactions with one another on a social and economic level (World Bank, 1992; Fukuyama, 2013).

Good governance:

Evaluating public institutions' ability to manage resources, conduct public affairs, and ensure the implementation of human rights in a way that is mostly free from abuse and corruption and with proper regard for the rule of law is known as good governance. The World Bank first presented the idea in its 1992 study, "Governance and Development." According to the study, effective governance is crucial to the creation and maintenance of an environment that promotes robust and equitable growth. It also serves as a complement to intelligent economic strategies. According to the World Bank, good governance includes the following elements: accountability, skill and

effectiveness in managing the public sector, a legal foundation for development, and information and transparency (World Bank, 1992).

At a UN meeting at Bretton Woods, New Hampshire, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) was established. The IMF stated in 1996 that "supporting good governance in all its forms, including by upholding the law, enhancing the effectiveness and accountability of the public sector, and combating corruption, are critical components of a framework within which economies may develop" (International Monetary Fund, 1996). According to the IMF, inefficient economic governance—either excessive or insufficient regulation—is the root source of corruption inside economies (International Monetary Fund, 2005). Countries must have specific good governance measures in place as evaluated by the IMF to be eligible for loans from the IMF.

For making the government more efficient, effective, and accountable, Worldwide Governance Indicators developed by Daniel Kaufmann and Aart Kraay in 1996 comprise six broad dimensions of governance under the auspices of the World Bank, which are as follows (Kaufmann & Kraay, 2002):

- Voice and Accountability.
- Government Effectiveness.
- Regulatory Quality.
- Rule of Law.
- Control of Corruption.
- Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism.

The United Nations (UN) is becoming more involved in promoting good governance. Former UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan asserts that "good governance" entails upholding human rights and the rule of law, bolstering democracy, and fostering openness and administrative ability. The UN adheres to eight principles to put this into practice (UNESCAP, 2009):

1. Participation - Through genuine local groups or representatives, people should be allowed to express their own thoughts.
2. Rule of Law - Laws pertaining to human rights should be enforced impartially.

3. Consensus-oriented: Mediates divergent interests in order to achieve a general consensus over the community's best interests.
4. Equity and inclusivity - Everyone should have the chance to maintain or enhance their wellbeing.
5. Effectiveness and Efficiency - Institutions and processes should be able to create outcomes that satisfy community requirements while making the most efficient use of available resources.
6. Accountability - Public and institutional stakeholders should keep government agencies, the commercial sector, and civil society groups responsible.
7. Transparency - Information must be observable, intelligible, and available to the general public.
8. Responsive - Institutions and processes should be served to the needs of all stakeholders.

Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act, 2010:

Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act, 2010 is an Act based on the Right to Services that was passed by the Madhya Pradesh State Government named as “Madhya Pradesh Lok Sewaon ke Pradan Ki Guarantee Adhiniyam, 2010”. It was published in the Madhya Pradesh Gazette on the date of August 18, 2010. This Act's goal is to provide the state's citizens with public services within a "stipulated time limit.". It includes the following provisions that make itself a people-oriented Act (GoM.P., 2010):

- i. The state's eligible citizens are given the ability to request services under this Act and are given a deadline within which to do so. The "Designated Officer" will be in charge of offering the services.
- ii. The allotted time period will begin on the earlier of the day the application is submitted to the subordinate who is authorized to receive applications or the date the designated officer receives the application.
- iii. The designated officer will either offer services within the specified time limit or may reject the application. If the application is rejected, designated officials must give the applicant with written notice of the reason(s) for the denial.

- iv. An applicant whose application had rejected may appeal to the first appeal officer within 30 days of the refusal. If the applicant presents adequate justifications for why they are unable to file an appeal, the "first appellate authority" could permit filing an appeal after the expiry date. The first appeal officer may reject the application or direct the designated officer to render services at a specific time.
- v. Within 60 days of the preceding decision, an applicant who received a refusal from the first appeal officer may appeal again to the "Second appeal officer." If the petitioner has good cause to postpone an appeal, the second appellate authority may grant the request after the deadline has passed. The application may be rejected by the Second Appellate Authority or the designated official may be ordered to perform services.
- vi. According to this Act, designated and first appellate officials can be penalized for delivering services late or not at all. The designated officials will be fined between 250 to 5000 rupees if they don't provide the requested services or took too long to deliver services. The first appellate authority shall be fined not less than 500 rupees and maximum 5000 rupees if it fails to make a decision within the allotted period. This Act gives them a fair chance to be heard before any fines are assessed.
- vii. On the order of the second appellate authority, the applicant may receive some compensation, but it couldn't be more than the fine levied on the service provider authority.
- viii. With regard to choices and acts performed in good faith, this Act offers protection to public authorities.

The State Government may amend this Act in any way it sees fit, but every choice must first be presented to the legislative assembly for approval.

Additional initiatives taken by Madhya Pradesh Government to implement MPPSGA, 2010:

For successful implementation of MPPSGA, 2010 Madhya Pradesh Government started many supportive programs, these are as follows (MP e-District Portal):

- a. **Smart Governance:** The MP Government put in place a framework for good governance, which includes things like reliable transparency, trustworthy monitoring and evaluation system, and precise accountability.
- b. **Government Process Reengineering (GPR):** It is an application of ICT for governance. It tracks the provision of alerting services using business intelligence and data analytics techniques.
- c. **MP e-district Portal:** It is a platform of the MP government that unifies all of the district administration services and automates internal working procedures. Various departments and their services are integrated, including the services of tehsil/block level and local government level.
- d. **Samadhan Ek Din:** This initiative was launched in March 2018 to ensure prompt delivery of certain notified services in one day through single window shops known as Lok Seva Kendra (LSK) in a reliable, efficient, transparent and integrated manner.
- e. **CM Dashboard:** “It is an integrated portal, visually representing the key performance indicators of approximately 30 departments and empowering the administration in making informed decisions for citizens through appropriate initiatives.”
- f. **CM helpline:** “A helpline was established to enable agile and responsive governance in the state to address resident’s issues, concerns and take suggestions, regarding government schemes and services. A citizen can call up toll-free number 181 to register their grievances, which is then attended/resolved by designated officials within a particular time frame.”
- g. **MP MyGov:** “Introduced by the Chief Minister, Shivraj Singh Chouhan, in August 2017, MP MyGov is a citizen engagement platform that empowers people to associate with the government and contribute towards good governance through group discussions, polls, contests, blogs etc. The portal has successfully registered almost 33,000 users and nearly 4,000 submissions for various contests and discussions.”

Figure 1: Initiatives Taken by Madhya Pradesh Government to Implement MPPSGA 2010.

Objective: To examine does Right to Service Act helps to establish Good Governance.

Literature Review:

Bose (2021) The concept of the Right to Public Services has been developed from the citizens' charter. It is a document providing information about services provided by an organization to its beneficiaries. The enactment of the Right to Services as a Public Service Delivery Act provides a legal framework to direct officials and acts as a safeguard for beneficiaries from the perils of bureaucracy.

Singh, Kumar, & Arrawatia (2019) In order to improve service delivery in India, it is important to focus on the supply side of public service delivery. The government needs to ensure that bureaucracy is made accountable for their service delivery. This can be achieved by introducing measures to make sure that the bureaucracy is held to account for their actions. This can include introducing performance management systems, performance incentives, and increased transparency and accountability. Additionally, the government needs to promote citizens'

involvement in the service delivery process. This can be done by providing opportunities for citizens to participate in decision-making, by introducing participatory budgeting, and by creating mechanisms for citizens to monitor and evaluate service delivery. Finally, the government needs to invest in the technological infrastructure necessary for e-governance systems to be effective and efficient. This includes investing in the infrastructure and systems necessary for data collection, analysis and dissemination. By introducing such measures, it is possible to improve the service delivery system in India and ensure that citizens receive the services they are entitled to.

Julius (2011) states that public services are those services provided by governments to the public, such as education, health services, sewage, trash disposal, and street cleaning. Public service delivery is the process of making these public goods and services available to the expected stakeholders or the general public. It relies on the ability of the government to deliver, the nature of government in power, the nature of public administration and management and the needs of the community or citizens. In order for public service delivery to be successful, the government must have adequate resources and finance in order to provide these services.

United Nations ESCAP (2009) The literature on governance is vast and varied, ranging from philosophical and theoretical discussions to empirical studies of different governance models. Philosophical discussions have focused on the definition of governance, its relationship to democracy and the state, and the role of the citizen in the governance process. Theoretical analysis has examined the relationship between governance and economic development, social justice, and human rights. Empirical studies have looked at the effectiveness of various governance models in different contexts and the success of various institutional reforms.

International Monetary Fund (1996) asserted that good governance is essential for a nation to achieve economic development. This involves observing the law, improving the performance and responsibility of the public sector, and combating corruption. The IMF has also suggested that bad governance, whether it be too much or too little regulation, is at the heart of corruption within an economy. Therefore, in order to qualify for loans from the IMF, countries must demonstrate they have the necessary good governance measures in place.

World Bank (1996) measuring good governance is a complex task that requires analysis of multiple indicators. Common indices such as the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators,

the Index of Public Integrity and Freedom House's Freedom in the World report are widely used, and measure good governance by examining different aspects, such as citizen participation, political stability, government effectiveness, rule of law, and corruption.

World Bank (1992) good governance is essential for fostering an environment that facilitates strong and equitable expansion. Additionally, it is seen as a supplement to wise economic plans. The World Bank has laid out several components for effective governance, such as accountability, proficiency in managing the public sector, legal structures that support development, and information and transparency.

World Bank (1989) The concept of governance involves the exercise of power in order to manage the economic and social resources of a nation for its development. In basic terms, a reliable and open structure of regulations and institutions must exist to manage the activities of both private and public entities.

Data Source and Research Methodology:

This study is based on primary sources while secondary sources have been used to substantiate the study. A holistic approach has been adopted where various research tools and techniques followed. It is a mixed approach of research methodology. Detailed methodology is followed:

- i. **Ex-post facto method** followed for describing the implementation and mechanism of MPPSGA, 2010. It will be helpful to increase the existing knowledge about Right to Services to citizens and will make a better understanding about it.
- ii. **Analytical approach** has been used for comparison of MPPSGA, 2010 with World Wide Governance Indicators that are useful to analyze and evaluate MPPSGA, 2010 in context of Good Governance.
- iii. **Quantitative** research approach has been followed to justify MPPSGA, 2010 fulfils the requirement of Governance Indicators, with the help of published official data.
- iv. **Qualitative** research approach has been followed to discover the underlying motive and objectives of MPPSGA, 2010 and its implementation success, using in depth interviews of government officials and citizens, non-participative and mass observation.

All the above methods made it an empirical and analytical study that relies on the experiences and observations of government officers, citizens, and researchers.

Data Source:

The primary study has been conducted during July-August 2021, in Bhopal district of Madhya Pradesh State in India. 27 Government officers, 150 Citizens and 20 outsource Agencies have been interviewed. Non-participative and mass observation method followed on 4 Lok Seva Kendras (single window service provider shops) for empirical purpose.

Table 1: Tools and Techniques used to fulfil parameters:

Tools and Techniques used to fulfil parameters		
S. NO.	Parameters	Tools used in evaluation of MPPSGA, 2010
1.	Voice and Accountability	
	1.a. Voice	Provision of hearing/Appeal
	1.b. Accountability	
	1.b.i. Answerability	Provided services and imposed Penalties
	1.b. ii. Enforceability	orders of Appellate Authorities
	1.b. iii. Transparency	ICT Tools, Information Access
2.	Governance effectiveness	Implementation and citizen acceptance, timely delivery
3.	Regulatory Quality	Appellate authorities and time taken
4.	Rule of Law	Presence of law and its implementation
5.	Control of Corruption	Accountability, Transparency, time bound, penalization, out sourcing
6.	Political Stability and Absence of Violence	Did Not Consider Under the mentioned Act (MPPSGE 2010).

Analysis of MPPSGA, 2010 on the basis of Worldwide Governance Indicator (WGI):

Voice and Accountability:

In the analysis of the Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA) 2010, voice refers to the extent of citizens' participation and engaging in public discourse. It encompasses the freedom of expression, association, and access to a free media. Accountability, on the other hand, focuses on the responsibility and answerability of service providers under the MPPSGA 2010. It involves holding service providers accountable for delivering the promised services to the citizens. Both Voice and Accountability are crucial parameters for determining good governance and are central to evaluating the effectiveness of the MPPSGA 2010.

Voice:

Citizens' voice and service providers' accountability are important parameters to determine Good Governance. Citizens need an effective voice to express their ideas on various platforms to convey the government. The capacity of citizens to express their opinions and be heard by the government through formal or informal means, in writing or verbally, is frequently referred to as having a voice (Menocal & Sharma, 2008).

According to Goetz and Jenkins (2002, 2005), for three interrelated reasons Voice matters: First of all, having a voice has intrinsic worth; individuals should have the right to express their opinions. Second, Voice is a fundamental component of accountability. Third, it is crucial for communities to come together in order to establish the standards — the principles and rules of justice and morality - by which the conduct of those in positions of authority will be assessed.

In the context of the Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA) 2010, the provision of a two-step appellate system serves as a mechanism for hearing the voice of citizens on behalf of the government. This system allows citizens to appeal to the 1st appellate authority if they did not receive the services guaranteed under the Act within the specified time frame. If the decision of the 1st appellate authority is not satisfactory to the citizen, they have the option to appeal to the 2nd appellate authority. Furthermore, if a citizen remains dissatisfied with the verdict of the 2nd appellate authority, they can pursue legal action by filing a suit in court.

These provisions of the MPPSGA 2010 are designed to strengthen the voice of citizens by providing them with channels to address grievances and seek redressal for any lapses in service delivery. As millions of people's lives can be impacted by successful public policies, it is imperative that even the most vulnerable groups have their voices heard in the implementation and enforcement of such policies. By ensuring that citizens have access to a fair and transparent appellate process, the MPPSGA 2010 aims to uphold accountability and responsiveness in public service delivery, ultimately contributing to the promotion of good governance.

Figure 2: Citizens', Appellate Authority and Service Providers' relation that strengthen citizens' Voice.

Accountability:

Accountability is the process of holding individuals or groups responsible for their actions. It involves transparency, which ensures that decisions and actions are open and visible to the public, as well as enforceability, which means that there are mechanisms in place to ensure that individuals or groups are held accountable for their actions. The relationship between decision-makers and citizens relies on transparency, accountability, and enforceability to maintain accountability. These principles help to ensure that those in positions of authority are held responsible for their decisions and actions, fostering trust and integrity in governance processes (Menocal & Sharma, 2008).

Figure 3: Accountability Cycle through MPPSGA, 2010.

There are three interrelated dimensions of accountability in administration (Ocampo & Arteaga, 2014):

- a. Answerability: It refers to the obligation of the administration to acknowledge, explain, and justify their actions and decisions to the public. It involves providing clear and comprehensive explanations for the rationale behind administrative actions, ensuring transparency and accountability in governance processes. Answerability enhances trust between the government and citizens by promoting openness and clarity in decision-making, ultimately contributing to effective and responsive governance.

Table 2: Applications Status (at the primary level) Under MPPSGA 2010:

Time	Number of the received applications	Number of the Applications solved on time			Number of Applications solved after time		
		Provided services	denied services	total	provided services	denied services	Total
25/09/2012 to 31/03/2013	1963586	1392558	440713	1833271	100554	29761	130315
01/04/2013 to 31/03/2014	7761139	5534892	1268363	6803255	624092	333791	957883
01/04/2014 to 31/03/2015	14358746	12801839	1011938	13813777	398194	115076	513270
01/04/2015 to 31/03/2016	12631537	10419683	1587737	12007420	388699	184159	572858
01/04/2016 to 31/03/2017	6191003	5445010	423901	5868911	205241	47733	252974
01/04/2017 to 07/11/2017	3992172	3594206	184385	3778591	30769	4177	34946
Total	46898183	39188188	4917037	44105225	1747549	714697	2462246

Source: e-District Branch of Madhya Pradesh Government.

The data reveals that out of 46,898,183 services demanded, only 44,105,225 services were provided on time. Additionally, 2,462,246 services were provided after the specified time frame. However, there is no information available regarding 2,078,261 services, which were not provided either on time or after the allotted time. While this constitutes only 4.43% of the total demanded services, in the context of good governance, it is expected that all demanded services are fulfilled. It is imperative to hold the authority answerable for not providing these services, ensuring transparency and accountability in governance practices.

- b. Enforceability: It refers to the ability of higher authorities to compel subordinates to adhere to their duties. It implies that administrators are bound by rules and laws and must operate

within the legal framework, subject to the sanctions imposed by the law. This concept underscores the idea that individuals in administrative positions are accountable for their actions and decisions, and they can be held responsible if they fail to comply with the established rules and regulations. Enforceability ensures that governance structures function effectively and that those responsible for upholding the law are held accountable for their actions.

Table 3: Application Status (at the appellate authority level), Time (25/09/2012 to 07/11/2017)

Appellate Authorities	Number of the received applications	Number of the Applications solved on time			Number of Applications solved after time		
		Provided services	denied services	Total	provided services	denied services	Total
1 st Appellate Authority	73782	15580	38438	54018	5196	13788	18984
2 nd Appellate Authority	937	260	448	708	Data Not Available	Data Not Available	Data Not Available

Source: e-District Branch of Madhya Pradesh Government.

The data indicates that the first appellate authority enforced its decisions on 54,018 services provided on time and 18,984 services provided after the stipulated time, out of a total of 73,782 services demanded. Additionally, the second appellate authority enforced its decisions on 708 out of 937 services demanded. However, there is no available data regarding the remaining services demanded and their status, particularly those that were not provided either on time or after the allocated time. While the percentage of services with enforced decisions is significant, the lack of information about the status of the remaining demanded services underscores the importance of transparency and accountability in governance processes. It is essential to ensure that all services demanded are accounted for and addressed in accordance with established procedures to uphold principles of good governance.

- c. **Transparency:** Transparency is a critical component for measuring accountability, particularly in the implementation of the Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA) 2010. The government utilizes Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools such as the MPOne Portal and the eDistrict portal to facilitate the implementation process. The services outlined under this Act are also covered by the Right to Information Act 2005, enabling citizens to access information through the RTI and eDistrict portals. This integration of technology and legal frameworks enhances transparency by making the process more accessible and visible to the public, thereby fostering accountability in governance practices.

Government Effectiveness:

Government effectiveness is evaluated based on the quality of the civil service and its independence from political influence, the effectiveness of policy formulation and implementation, and the government's commitment to its stated policies (World Bank, 1996).

In the context of the MPPSGA 2010, government effectiveness can be assessed by the implementation of the act, the civil servants' responsibility to deliver services punctually, and the public's acceptance of the act.

The following graph and pie chart illustrate that 97% of service requests (applications received) were resolved on time, with 73% of requested services provided and 24% denied. Only 3% of service requests were addressed after the designated time. This data suggests that the MPPSGA, 2010 has made civil servants more accountable and committed to serving citizens promptly, thereby establishing effective governance within civil service and public service provision.

Figure 4: Service Delivery Status since 2012 to 2017.

Figure 5: Percent-wise service delivery status since 25/09/2012 to 07/11/2017.

Regulatory Quality (RQ):

The capacity of the government to create and enforce sensible laws and policies that foster the growth of the private sector is crucial. In the Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA) 2010, provisions have been established for appellate authorities to ensure regulatory quality. The Act specifies two-tier appellate authorities for each notified service, offering citizens the opportunity to appeal to the 1st appellate authority within 30 days from the date of application rejection at the preliminary stage or upon expiration of the notified time limit. If dissatisfied with the decision of the 1st appellate authority, citizens can further appeal to the 2nd appellate authority within 60 days of the previous verdict.

Moreover, to enhance the accountability, responsiveness, and quality of the 1st appellate authority, the 2nd appellate authority has the power to impose penalties if it fails to ensure service delivery within the stipulated time frame. The 1st appellate authority may be subject to financial penalties of Rs. 500 per day, not exceeding Rs. 5,000, if it fails to provide a valid reason for the non-delivery of services. These measures aim to strengthen regulatory quality and ensure effective governance in the delivery of public services under the MPPSGA 2010.

Rule of Law (RL)

The scope of literature on the rule of law is extensive, with various hypotheses and interpretations being put forward. (Johnston, 2002) defines the rule of law as the execution of governmental power based on and guided by published standards that reflect commonly accepted social values and prevent favoritism. (Fukuyama, 2013), on the other hand, distinguishes the rule of law from "rule by law," which is the utilization of law and bureaucracy by the executive as a means of power. The United Nations (2004) defines the rule of law as a system of governance in which all persons, entities, public and private, including the state, are held accountable to laws that are openly declared, evenly enforced, and independently judged, and which are in line with international human rights norms and standards. This definition highlights the necessity of complying with the principles of the supremacy of the law, equal treatment under the law, responsibility to the law, fairness in law implementation, separation of powers, involvement in decision-making, legal assurance, evasion of arbitrariness, and procedural and legal transparency.

Analyze the degree to which government employees respect and uphold social norms, in particular the effectiveness of the enforcement of contracts, property rights, the police, and the courts, as well as the possibility of crime and violence (World Bank, 1996).

Madhya Pradesh government passed a bill on Right to Service in 2010 in its legislative assembly, named as Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act, 2010. An Act itself a law and its implementation follows the “Rule of Law”.

Control of Corruption (CC)

Measure the level of corruption, both small-scale and large-scale, that occurs when public authority is used for personal benefit (World Bank, 1996). Invest in institutions and policies; imported models frequently do not work. Sensible rules and practices that allow for change while making the best use of tried-and-true traditions and legacies are necessary for lasting improvement in how a government delivers services.

In order to control corruption in governance, it is necessary that the responsibilities of the administrators should be fully ensured and they should be held accountable for their work. There should be maximum transparency in the system, as well as there should be a clear time limit for service delivery. Apart from this, reasonable penalties should be imposed on the administrators who fail to comply with their responsibilities. It is also observed that outsourcing some functions to other agencies can also reduce corruption to some extent.

In this context, the above parameters have been analysed in detail in this study. On the one hand, the analysis of accountability, transparency, punctuality, and penalty has been presented above. On the other hand, in Madhya Pradesh, arrangements have been made for public service centers based on common windows, which are being operated by outsourced agencies, to take applications from applicants and provide final service. Thus, we see that adequate steps have been taken here to control corruption.

Discussion:

The Right to Services/Public Services Guarantee Act (RTS/PSGA) represents a commendable initiative aimed at delivering public services within specified timeframes and holding government servants and frontline service providers accountable. Upon analysing the

Madhya Pradesh Public Service Guarantee Act (MPPSGA) 2010 alongside the Worldwide Governance Indicators, it becomes evident that this Act directly supports five indicators and fulfils their requirements. However, one indicator pertaining to stable government and the absence of violence is not directly met by the MPPSGA 2010. Nevertheless, the fulfilment of the aforementioned five indicators contributes significantly to establishing a stable government capable of managing violence. Thus, the MPPSGA 2010 indirectly justifies the sixth indicator, highlighting its role in promoting good governance and stability.

During interviews and analysis of respondents' responses several points found and experienced that are as follows:

- i. MPPSGA, 2010 imposes a time bound duty to serve the services while there is no scientific division of works. In simple words, humans have a limited capacity to perform any task in a certain period and these limitations restrict them to do over-work. In case of a large amount of applications arrival in a short period, responsible authority will not be capable to fulfil all demands in a short-notified period.
- ii. Time limit begins from the application submission date or the date when authorized person receives application, while there are no provision and record about the rejection of application before submission. It means if responsible officer denies the submission of application, then there is no obligation of service delivery and this is not recorded in government data also.
- iii. This Act is based on the dis-incentive system, which obey stick rule only. Most of the theories follows carrot and stick rule, carrot indicates incentives for good performance and stick demonstrates punishment for bad performance. While in this Act, incentives and motivator factors did not cover for outstanding performance, only penalization has been provisioned for deny/delay service delivery without any valid reason.
- iv. Citizens are still facing bad evils of governance, due to physical distance of government offices and less awareness about Information and Communication Technology (ICT), they are Compelled to take help from middlemen, that again helps the existence of corruption.

Suggestions:

After a holistic study of MPPSGA, 2010 including implementation analysis, ground level field work and its analysis with WGI, researcher experienced several lacunas that may be implemented with MPPSGA, 2010. Those will be helpful to establish good governance. These are as follows:

- i. This Act should be employees oriented also rather than to be citizens oriented only.
- ii. There should be a clear determination of the work to be done by the employees on a daily basis, so that human limitations do not become a hindrance in this.
- iii. Extensive public awareness programs should be run to make citizens aware, in which training should also be given in the use of ICT/ICT'es.
- iv. The government should reach every citizen's doorstep. For this there should be optimum use of ICT and ICT'es.
- v. There should be a provision of third-party audit system under MPPSGA, 2010. So that optimum accountability can be fix.
- vi. For more government-effectiveness, there should be contracting out some services with private agencies, NGOs and Civil Societies etc.
- vii. For enhancing regulatory-quality, there should be an independent body that will supervise, direct and investigate all the three layers of service delivery authorities, i.e., designated officers, 1st and 2nd appellate authorities etc... Although MP Government established body named as "Madhya Pradesh Rajya Lok Seva Abhikaran", but it does not have enough powers and authorities to control regulatory quality.
- viii. For controlling corruption, government started to use of ICT, but entries can be manipulated easily by authorities, and the previous data will not be available for further use. To overcome such kind of problems government should apply such kind of technologies that will not allow deletion or manipulation of data. For each correction there should be new entries, so that both data will be available and accountability could be defining for each correction, that will control the corruption.
- ix. For rule of law, existence of any law is not enough, its proper and efficient implementation and periodic review of it also necessary.

Limitations:

This study focused on the establishment of good governance through MPPSGA, 2010 on the parameters of Worldwide Governance Indicators. WGI includes six indicators, hence all these considered in study. Along with this, United Nations presented eight parameters of good governance those are not included, although some common parameters analyzed in the study. For analysis of each WGI, World Bank suggested many parameters but all are not utilized, some specific parameters are used that are relevant with respect to MPPSGA, 2010.

Conclusion:

From the above discussion, it is clear that MPPSGA, 2010 alone is not able to fulfill all parameters of WGI, one indicator “Stable Government and Absence of Violence” is not directly accomplished. Hence it is necessary to adopt a wider perspective of executions where more than one tools and applications must be utilized. It is required to comprise most innovative and updated technologies in governance. Use of Block-Chain technology reckon in ICT that will prohibit manipulation of data and will increase the transparency in the governance process.

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